

PROSPECTS OF CULTIVATION AND PROCESSING OF KOVUL UNIQUE PLANT

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ABSTRACT

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-139 dated 20.05.2022 measures to create an additional value chain by supporting the effective use of the raw material base of medicinal plants and processing. Effective use of the base of medicinal plant raw materials, wide use of medicinal plants in the prevention and treatment of diseases, organization of deep processing by supporting business entities establishing cultural plantations of medicinal plants, and additional We aim to create a value chain. From 2022 to 2026, it is planned to establish plantations of new medicinal plants on an area of 36,000 hectares.

KEYWORDS:

Cabbage, cabbage, fruit, flower, seed, stem, medicine, pharmaceutical, watermelon, medicinal, grass, soil, fertile, sand, sandy, arid, cold, low temperature, desert, mountain and mountain ash, alkaloids, carbohydrate, ascorbic acid.

Introduction. At present, the interest in medicinal plants in the world is increasing day by day. For this reason, we aimed our scientific work at studying the koval plant. Our people call this plant kavar. Capparis spinosa (Capparis spinosa L.) is a semi-shrub belonging to the Capparis family. The stem and branches are horizontal, the leaf is oval, the flower is large, white or light pink. The fruit is red fleshy and has many seeds. Crimea, Caucasus, Central Asia, Shim. Widely distributed in rocky areas of Africa and the Mediterranean. Jean. It is cultivated in Europe. Buds and fruits of K. are pickled or salted and put in oven. The fruit contains 18% protein and 36% oil. It is a multi-seeded berry that grows in deserts and hills, on roadsides, on walls, among crops, and its fruits are fleshy, up to 2 cm long. Seeds ripen in July-August. The fruits of this medicinal plant contain saponins, alkaloids, 32.9 percent carbohydrates, 150 mg of

ascorbic acid, 3.75 percent oil, stachydrin alkaloid in the root bark. including Uzbekistan, Pakistan and India. This plant is cultivated in France, Spain, Italy, Algeria and Cyprus, Greece and North America, and is a decoration of landscapes. The plant is named after the Dashti-Kavir desert in Iran. Because sorghum is the most common plant in these regions. In scientific sources, the original origin of this plant is associated with the Dashti Kavir desert in Iran. Because sedum is the most common plant in this area. It is cultivated in France, Spain, Italy, Algeria and Cyprus, Greece and North America. It grows naturally in the mountainous regions of our country. Currently, our republic is widely distributed in several districts of Jizzakh region, including Zomin, Gallaorol, Forish, Sharof Rashidov, in addition, many species can be found in Buloqboshi of Andijan region, Chust and Kosonsoy districts of Namangan region, mountain and sub-mountain regions of Tashkent region. and they are widely used in medicine by local people. This thorn bush, which grows freely in the ground, does not choose a place, according to its mechanical composition, it grows well in sandy and loamy lands, and in soils with low fertility. In addition, the plant is resistant to external factors, i.e. drought and cold. It grows from May to October. It blooms piece by piece. Then a one-celled fleshy berry bears fruit. In addition to being a medicinal plant, cranberry is also used in food. Buds, buds, and developing fruits of saffron are marinated in acetic acid and used in food as a medicine known as capers. Hindus call the snake by the names of cobra, kabra or kabarra, and they like to eat food prepared with the addition of plant organs.

The entire above-ground and underground biomass of this plant is considered medicinal in the pharmaceutical and food industries. Therefore, it is highly valued as a valuable raw material in the pharmaceutical industry. The fruit contains saponins, alkaloids, carbohydrates, ascorbic acid, oil, stachydrin alkaloid in the root bark. In early spring, the root dug up is dried, and medicine is prepared for allergy sufferers. Even before the flowering season, a decoction is made that is food for allergies. Freshly cut and brewed as a tea, the branches are a good antiseptic. Arabs and ancient Greeks used such properties.

In our country, Ibn Sina, the sultan of medicine, wrote down the methods of preparing medicines from this type of plant, which are useful in the treatment of many diseases. It is noted that the tincture obtained from the root part of the plant is a cure for hepatitis, the stem and leaves are a vaccine for skin diseases, and the iodine contained in the fruit is beneficial to people suffering from measles. In the world pharmaceutical industry, the preparation of drugs based on these recommendations is widely established. Kovul has been used in folk

medicine. Mainly, it was used in the treatment of purulent wounds, angina pectoris, thyrotoxicosis, gout, and diabetes. Koval is also used in the food industry. Hindus enjoy eating dishes prepared with its fruit, while in French cuisine, marinated cauliflower florets are a very important spice. In our country, kovol "watermelons" were dried and used instead of sugar in winter. Along with vitellotonnato, which is cold-dried veal in the Italian way, "tonnato" cabbage, which certainly contains cabbage, should be served. And in Great Britain, if you don't use hot cabbage with cabbage to increase the palatability of mutton, it's easy to lose customers. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev is paying special attention to increasing the role and importance of the agricultural sector in the sustainable development of our economy, ensuring food security, and increasing the export potential of our country. In years like this year, when there is a shortage of water, it is beneficial in every way to open a reserve of such drought-resistant crops. The main thing is that the flower of the plant is rich in nectar and attracts the birds. Therefore, the development of the woodworking industry opens the way to the prospect of several more branches, the opening of many new jobs, and the creation of an additional source of income. We are conducting our scientific work in the conditions of low productivity of Navoi vilozti.

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